

Environmental and Economic Impacts of Hydropower Plants

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Abstract:

The generating of electricity is the primary application of hydroelectric energy. The major components of hydroelectric power plants are dams, rivers, and turbines. Plants use dams to construct reservoirs that store water. The Importance of Hydropower In contrast to wind and solar, hydropower offers dispatch able electricity using low-risk methods. Hydropower is the most dependable and well-established source of clean, renewable energy.

The potential energy of the water turbine and generator generates

the vast bulk of hydroelectric power. One advantage of hydroelectric power is that it allows you to control the river flow downstream. Every country has difficulties due to how much of the total energy consumption it makes up. Encountered in the development of hydropower are noted. Connected to hydropower plants have the potential to offer additional advantages including flood control, irrigation, and water supply. Furthermore, hydropower is seen as a potential and sustainable source of energy, with a global economic influence.

Keywords: *Hydropower, environment, renewable energy, Economic impact sustainable.*

Introduction

Nowadays the environmental studies' most prominent problems of climate change and health risks force all countries to implement sustainable development plans a study from. Finding solutions to environmental challenges such as climate change and global warming is now critical if sustainable development goals are to be reached. One of the efficient ways to manage environmental problems and enhance environmental sustainability is to introduce and promote green practices and renewable energy technology. (Athayde, et al. 2019)

Switching and heading for green energy, using wave and water energy has lately acknowledged with high attention worldwide. These energy sources have encountered ongoing difficulties due to economic expansion and environmental protection, conferring to statistics supplied by

the Policy of Indonesian National Energy. Besides promoting, the use of renewable energy faces two major obstacles: first, it is intermittent and difficult to govern; and second, the generation mostly depends on the three-dimensional distribution. Due to this circumstance, the amount of renewable energy in the globe has increased, particularly in the Germany and United States, where 13 thirteen percent and 25 twenty-five percent of production services are shared, correspondingly. (Chala, et al.2019)

Hydropower is a desirable and viable alternative for generating electricity that is gaining popularity around the world due to its numerous benefits. The main advantage of hydropower over other renewable energy sources like wind and solar is its steady supply. Hydropower facilities benefit from the flexibility of their operation in electrical grids. Additionally,

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hydropower's comparatively inexpensive cost of electricity generation is another aspect that increases its competitiveness and appeal. Furthermore, electricity can be created from naturally flowing water rather than fossil fuels or other traditional energy sources (as in the case of conventional power plants), which supports its purity and results in less absolutes of pollutants into the atmosphere. Growing body of research shows that, in comparison to other predictable types of power generation systems, the emissions connected to hydropower projects are relatively lower.

Hydropower is a flexible technology since it may also benefit society and the economy. A hydroelectric project can be constructed to achieve a variety of goals, such as energy

production, irrigation, flood control, and tourism, to name a few. As a result, the social, economic, and environmental structures of a region or country are critical for the development of hydroelectric facilities. (Fig. 1). The main goal of a hydropower plant is often electricity production, which promotes regional development by utilizing naturally flowing water to produce energy. It is advantageous for a country to compete in the carbon trading market, obtain carbon credits, and then satisfy its emission reduction targets. Aside from these challenges, irrigation, flood control, fisheries, tourism, and other job sources are all linked to hydropower development, which has a positive impact on the local society and economy (Nautiyal&Goel,2020).

Figure 1. Hydropower projects Associated by Factors
 Source: Nautiyal & Goel (2020)

The importance of hydropower is expanding, and interest in this renewable energy source (RES) arises, among other things, from the need to moderate climate change and safeguard the environment. Hydropower produced 18% of the electricity in Europe in 2019; however, the percentage varied substantially between countries. Hydropower is most prevalent in Norway (95.7%) and Albania (100%) and least prevalent in Denmark, the Netherlands, and Estonia (share of domestic energy generation

less than 0.5%), according to 2019 data. Furthermore, climate change and the energy package are critical components of Europe's energy strategy because they promote the premise that consumers should obtain affordable, competitive, and sustainable energy. This strategy will alter the energy sector in Europe. It estimates that the targets, which include reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving national energy efficiency, and increasing the proportion of renewable energy

sources in total energy consumption, will be accomplished by 2020 and subsequently by 2030. (Tomczyk& Wiatkowski,2020)

It committed to implementing a directive that set the amount of RES consumption and constrained CO2 emissions into the atmosphere. Different nations confront different obstacles when implementing energy policies (particularly the increase in the share of RES), Improving international economic cooperation with other countries, boosting energy efficiency and independence, and providing tax breaks to individuals and businesses investing in environmentally friendly energy sources, streamlining administrative procedures, and decentralizing energy distribution. (Tomczyk& Wiatkowski,2020)

The first part of the article examines how much hydropower is used to produce electricity in various nations. (Tomczyk& Wiatkowski,2020) the difficulties of smart water resource management in relation to the objectives of environmental preservation and socioeconomic interests in many countries garnered particular attention. The dam impoundments that are connected to hydropower projects usually provide advantageous water supply, irrigation, and flood control services, in addition to supplying the power grid with electricity and other related services. However, hydropower projects may also negatively impact things like water quality, fish and wildlife resources, and river navigability.

Literature Review

According to Short-Term Energy Outlook (STEO). (2020) and The use of renewable energy is increasingly being included into the global energy mix as a result of falling costs and rising environmental consciousness. Many policies have been put in place to increase the use of renewable energy sources. One of the most well-established renewable energy methods is hydropower. Many countries, both with and without hydroelectric capability, have implemented it, and it has made a considerable contribution to the reduction of global carbon

emissions. (Kuriqi, et al. 2019) mentioned that to maximize the environmental and financial benefits of hydropower facilities, numerous research refined their operation and sizing. The most effective energy transporter, hydrogen, may be produced from a variety of raw materials, including water, according to a study by (Shiva, et al. 2019). Water electrolysis is the most environmentally friendly and pure technique of producing hydrogen. Water electrolysis also provides significant advantages including high cell productivity and hydrogen generation rates. Proton exchange membrane (PEM) water electrolysis is the greatest technique for creating hydrogen from renewable energy sources in terms of sustainability and environmental impact. (Bamisile, et al. 2020)

However, an International Energy Agency research found that building huge hydropower plants requires significant capital outlays and raises environmental problems, making them less appealing in today's global economy. Besides (Kabo-bah & Yeboah, 2018) highlighted how this circumstance has created a fantastic opportunity for small-scale hydropower projects (SHP). Furthermore, the European Commission classifies SHP production as Mini-Hydropower, Micro-Hydro, and Pico-Hydro for power outputs of less than 10 MW, 2 MW, 500 kW, and 10 kW, respectively (Balkhair & Rahman,2017).

Materials and Methods

The Knowledge Found in the Papers Used was Primarily Related to Hydropower, Environmental Protection, and Global Energy Policy

The main hydropower technologies are stream technology, pumped storage, rushing rivers, dammed reservoirs, and novel technology gravitational vortex (Nautiyal& Goel,2020). In this context, research in Europe primarily concentrates on the key components of electromechanical equipment, including turbines, pumps, and generators. The two primary types of turbines are impulse and response turbines. The bulk of reaction turbines, however, are axial flow turbines. In low head and

high flow settings, reaction turbines outperform impulse turbines. Water runs down a channel or penstock to a waterwheel or turbine, striking the bucket and turning the shaft. When producing electricity, a spinning shaft attached to an alternator or generator converts the motion of the shaft into electrical energy. (Chala et al,2019)

Hydroelectric power is more environmentally friendly than other energy sources since it emits less CO₂ and CH₄ and no SO₂, NO_x, or particulate matter. Low head canals have numerous benefits, such as no hydrological risk, close proximity to the load center, ease of access, and guaranteed water availability. Greenhouse gas emissions are also reduced by using hydroelectric power. It offers quicker benefits and energy security to developing nations with no significant adverse effects on the environment, land acquisition, or considerable running costs.

Hydropower is a renewable energy source that captures the kinetic or potential energy of water moving from higher to lower elevations. A technology is time-tested, developed, dependable, highly effective, and cost-efficient.

Among all known energy sources, hydropower has one of the highest conversion efficiencies; "water to wire" efficiency for modern power plants is typically >90%. A hydropower plant typically consists of civil structures for collecting, storing, and transporting water, as well as mechanical and electrical components for generating energy. In order to discover the best design, hydrology, hydraulics, and environmental implications must all be considered throughout planning and operation. A standard hydropower plant consists of an intake, a "head race" of tunnels and/or pipes, a power station with electrical and mechanical equipment ("Elmek"), and a "tail race" of tunnels and/or pipes to the exit. It may or may not feature a dam and a reservoir for water storage. Elmek equipment is made up of three main components: turbine(s), generator(s), and transformer(s). Other components will include gates and valves, electronic station gear, electrical cables, switchyards, and grid connections (Killingtveit & Anund). Fig. 2 is an Example of Electricity Production Using hydropower in Europe.

Figure 2. Electricity Production using hydropower in Europe
Source: International Energy Agency (2020)

As shown in Fig. 2 to analyze the data, statistical correlations between the study variables—population density, migration indicator,

birthrate, GDP per capita, human development index, and electricity consumption per capita—were studied. Social aspects (for example, the

share of hydropower supply, total RES energy, and the fraction of RES energy in total electricity consumption) and the percentage of RES energy derived from RES in total power consumption, as well as the amount of RES energy obtained by

RES in CO₂ emissions from industry, agriculture, and services per unit of GDP (average elevation, water resources per 0.1 km², annual precipitation per year, and specific discharge).

Figure 3. Shows Location Analyzed of Hydropower Plants
 Source: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/webmap/viewer.html>

Flood control, a natural habitat for fish and birds, agricultural water, and tourism-related activities are all provided by the reservoir. The demands of water law licenses, water law surveys, and water management instruction papers derived from Water Law regulations that apply the principles of the Water Framework Directive govern water management issues in these facilities. According to research, the hydropower plant, the fish pass, and the reservoir were unable to perform their intended functions due to the River's water level dropping above the reservoir, insufficient adaptation of water management documents, insufficient efficiency of the installed devices, and the inability of the hydropower plant, the fish pass, and the reservoir to accommodate fish. Furthermore, considering the conditions for fish passage, the design of the fish pass is inadequate.

The turbine sets were replaced due to a modification of the documentation by the Rural Development Program. Fig. 4 depicts the locations of a few hydropower plants.

Database Development

Based on 182 EA documents, which are typically created as "Developmental Analysis" documents, the database created for this study was created. as well as the FERC classification, final determination, and their associated economic data. Because of changes in file format (PDF, Microsoft Word document, or picture) and structure, each document was thoroughly evaluated. and all pertinent PM&E data were compiled in a Microsoft Excel Workbook, which will now be known as the EA Cost Database (different table formats, page and section numbering patterns, and section titles.

Figure 4. The Analysis's Main Findings are the Difficulties that Hydropower Development will Face

Each data row in the Cost Database represents a single mitigation activity intended to reduce the potential environmental impact of the development and operation, or ongoing operation, of a hydroelectric project. The data for each measure includes the stated initial capital cost, annual cost, entity promoting the measure, and judgment as to whether a certain measure is required for licensing. The initial capital cost is the one-time cost of implementing the solution, and it is occasionally accompanied with an annual cost that will be paid during the plant's life. However, not every policy incurs both of these costs. The expense of maintaining a minimal or aesthetically pleasing water flow, for example, is often only yearly.

Pumped storage hydropower (PSH)

Utility-scale energy storage has been available all around the world in the last century because to pumped storage hydropower (PSH). A PSH plant usually uses additional or low-cost

electricity to pump water from a lower reservoir to an upper reservoir, where it is stored.

When the grid requires more power or when electricity can be sold at a greater price, the water is returned to the lower reservoir via a powerhouse, producing electricity. Because the majority of modern PSH facilities were constructed in the middle of the twentieth century, they are either about to or have already expired.

The open-loop architecture used by these older plants, which are typically huge (>100 MW) and use it as a continuous link to a naturally flowing water feature, is described by FERC. Open-loop projects are often subject to severe EA requirements, similar to conventional hydroelectric dams, due to the rapid water transfer between the top and lower reservoirs, at least one of which is located on a natural body of water. (Werble, et al. 2021) Relicensed PSH programs are included in this category (RPSH). RPSH projects, like RPD projects, must submit

relicensing applications at least two years before the initial license expiration date and indicate relicensing plans at least five years ahead of time.

Results

Environmental Issues

Concerns among environmental decision-makers about the long-term profitability of hydroelectric projects are being renewed for environmental reasons. (Athayde, et al. 2019) Large reservoirs, complex construction projects, and a diverse variety of technologies and equipment used throughout the development and operating stages all have an ecological impact that cannot be ignored and need considerable financial investments. The development phase of a hydroelectric project requires a substantial amount of energy and

entails the transportation of numerous building materials due to the site-specific nature of the projects. Large water storage causes significant emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane because it accelerates the decomposition of vegetation on flooded land (CH₄). The reservoir's size is heavily influenced by the hydropower project's capacity and the geography in the area. Reservoirs have a substantial negative environmental impact because they damage residential neighborhoods, scenic areas, wildlife habitat, and agricultural land. The construction of the reservoir necessitates the migration of the inhabitants, making village restoration difficult. Hydropower plant operations have also caused environmental issues. Several studies have found that emissions during the operational phase are much higher than those during the construction phase.

Figure 5. Leading Nations in Hydropower Generation till 2018

Source: Renewable global status (2019)

To analyze the overall environmental effects of hydropower production, a variety of environmental indicators can be used. CO₂, CH₄, nitrous oxide (N₂O), ozone (O₃), and chlorofluorocarbons are examples of GHGs emitted (CFCs). is mostly to blame for the problems associated with climate change produced by global warming. Every GHG has a unique effect that changes depending on the gas's properties. Different GHGs can be represented as CO₂ equivalents using the global warming potential (GWP). GHG emissions,

namely CO₂ and CH₄, have an impact on agricultural and forestry land productivity while also contributing to the climate change challenge.

Biomass decomposes as a result of widespread forest and massive floodplains caused by land settlement, particularly in the construction of large reservoirs, contributing to GHG emissions from hydropower systems. Another critical component is the substantial community rehabilitation that comes with big reservoirs.

(Nautiyal & Goel, 2020). Even if the majority of the people is relocated to existing metropolitan regions, population density and other demands on the ecosystem would increase, potentially necessitating land removal. According to this point of view, land usage associated with hydropower projects involving large reservoirs has a double environmental impact. Given the hydropower project's use of the flooded region and forestland's ability to store carbon, this may make sense.

Fish-Friendly Hydropower Plants: Killingtveit

Dams and hydropower plants that hinder fish migration, restrict access to important rearing and spawning areas, potentially decrease or eradicate fish populations as a result, fish passage safety is a major consideration in hydropower

project environmental assessments. The two basic categories of technological advancement are as follows: Many large-scale hydropower projects necessitate tunnels and rock caverns, such as headrace/tailrace tunnels, access tunnels, powerhouses, surge shafts, power lines, and ventilation shafts. Since 1960, almost all large-scale hydropower projects in Norway have been built underground. Around 400 of the world's 500 underground hydropower facilities were discovered after they were discovered in 2002. It is shown in Fig. 6 typical tunnel system and rock caves layout; Figure 7 is an example of an underground power station. Tunneling technology has progressed from traditional drill-and-blast equipment to full-face tunnel boring machines (TBM), boosting speed and decreasing cost.

Figure 6. An Underground Hydropower Plant - Typical Layout of Tunnel System

Figure 7. Underground Hydropower Plant Brattset in Orkla River

Economy Impact

The implementation of a hydropower plan may in some cases need to consider not only the need for energy but also the potential for a source of irrigation and water supplies. Due to the lack of a multifunctional dam, the dam's discharged water is taken from a raw water intake downstream and used for water delivery. These dams can serve to decrease floods during the monsoon season in addition to providing a controlled base flow for water supply, irrigation, and navigation. The purpose of this multipurpose dam is to reduce the annual million-ringggit losses caused by monsoon floods at the end of the year. (Faizal, et al. 2017)

By creating roads and telecommunications infrastructure, the Scores development plan attempts to create a network of nodes for transportation and communication among firms. Third, governments strive to expand enterprises that provide a relatively less expensive source of electricity, such as internet companies. It is also meant to boost tourism, particularly near dam-created beaches and lakes. The plans to build these dams have increased demand for better roads and infrastructure, as well as the creation of new tourist destinations and eco-tourism-related businesses.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Study of the cost data for the environmentally responsible mitigation actions that are legally necessary. The hydroelectric sites discovered some notable tendencies in this research across metrics and project classifications. The greatest capital and cost projects were found to have the highest overall costs of measures, standardized by capacity, across all project classes. The expense of mitigating the environmental effects of hydroelectric projects is heavily influenced by the fact that many of these projects must meet with environmental criteria that did not exist when they were first approved decades ago. Furthermore, Hydropower projects with limited installed capacities frequently have greater costs per kilowatt than other Hydropower projects, which often have no capital and/or expenses for

a number of measures. The two categories with the highest installed capacity in the dataset, exhibit the reverse behavior. Although the total expenses are fairly high, projects typically have lower capital and operating costs per kilowatt than other project classes. Because these projects use closed-loop layouts that are not irrevocably linked to a natural water body, there is less need for environmental mitigation. RPSH projects, on the other hand, are often more mature and open loop, indicating that the facilities' lower costs per kilowatt are primarily attributable to their scale. PSH projects have the lowest costs for each type of mitigation, regardless of configuration, owing to economies of scale. This may be influenced by the data's small sample size for PSH programs.

Conclusion

Large reservoirs connected to hydropower plants have the potential to offer additional advantages including flood control, irrigation, and water supply. These advantages are significant but typically not taken into account in impact assessments. Since the utilization of additional advantages will be necessary for the hydropower systems to generate power. For instance, irrigation and water supply can influence the amount of water available for power generation, which further reduces output. Additionally, a lot of dams are constructed specifically for irrigation, flood control, and other purposes, which may provide little to no power. As a result, reservoirs rather than electricity generation are responsible for the majority of emissions.

Hydropower is recognized as a hopeful and sustainable source of energy, and its global volume is steadily expanding. Several studies, however, have cast doubt on its long-term durability. The current paper assesses all previous research on the subject of cost and sustainability assessments of hydropower plants. It also delves deeper into the results of a few research questions on these themes.

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